

Dating sediments by EPR using Al-h centre: a comparison between the properties of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse ($> 63 \mu\text{m}$) quartz grains

Zuzanna Kabacińska ^{1*} and Alida Timar-Gabor ^{1,2}

¹ Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babeş-Bolyai University, Treboniu Laurean 42, Cluj-Napoca 400271, Romania

² Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babeş-Bolyai University, Fântânele 30, Cluj-Napoca 400000, Romania

* Correspondence: zuziakab@gmail.com

Abstract: The possibility of EPR dating of sediments using Al-h signals of fine (4-11 μm) grains of quartz has not been previously discussed. Here the Al-h and peroxy EPR spectra of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90, 125-180 μm) sedimentary quartz from thoroughly investigated loess sites in Eastern Europe were examined. By comparing the experimental spectra with a simulated signal, we evaluated the overestimation observed when using the standard approach of Toyoda and Falguères [1] to measuring the Al-h intensity, for different doses of radiation up to 40 000 Gy. This overestimation, caused by the presence of peroxy signals, was much more pronounced for fine grains. Fine grains exhibited some additional dose-dependent signals, which for some samples caused a complete distortion of the Al-h spectra at high doses, making it impossible to measure the standard amplitude. We propose a new approach to measuring the Al-h signal intensity, focusing on the peak-to-baseline amplitude of the part of the signal at $g \approx 2.0603$, which is not affected by the peroxy signals, and therefore has a potential of providing more accurate results. The shapes of dose response curves constructed for coarse and fine grains using the new approach show a considerable similarity, suggesting that the Al-h centre formation in fine and coarse grains upon artificial radiation at room temperature follows the same pattern.

Keywords: Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR); Electron spin resonance (ESR); quartz; Al-h centre; fine grains; dose response curve

Citation:

<https://doi.org/10.3390/xxxxx>

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: © 2022 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Quartz (SiO_2) is a material of great importance in many areas of Earth sciences, as well as in the industry. As all crystals, it contains a vast number of point defects, which may be either intrinsic (involving only atoms of the host lattice – vacancies, interstitial atoms, and excess atoms) or extrinsic (belonging to foreign atoms in lattice and inter-lattice positions) [2, 3]. Those of most interest in the field of geochronology include Si- and O- vacancies and impurity related defects. Among the latter, Al^{3+} , always present in quartz, substitutes for Si^{4+} with charge compensation generally achieved by Li^+ , Na^+ or H^+ , which gives rise to $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ (where M^+ denotes an alkali metal or hydrogen ion) [4]. Ti^{4+} may substitute Si^{4+} in quartz with no charge compensation, creating $[\text{TiO}_4]^0$ [5]. Ge centre, namely $[\text{GeO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ (most notably $[\text{GeO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0$) is sometimes observed in irradiated natural quartz [5, 6]. A neutral oxygen vacancy can trap an electronic hole forming a paramagnetic oxygen vacancy (E' centre) [5, 6]. Performing systematic investigations of quartz using electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) (or electron spin resonance – ESR) spectroscopy, a method of high sensitivity, allowed gaining a deeper understanding of the mechanisms involved when the defects in quartz are subjected to irradiation.

EPR has been applied in dating geological and archaeological materials for over 40 years. Together with optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and thermoluminescence (TL), the so-called trapped-charge dating methods have been extensively used for dating sediments using quartz (e.g. [7–10]). Quartz records the amount of ionising radiation it has been exposed to as a latent signal within its crystal lattice, and therefore can be used as a natural dosimeter for quantifying the radiation history of materials. Irradiation at room temperature leads to dissociation of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ resulting in the formation of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{H}^+]^0$ and $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ [11]. $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$, also referred to as Al-hole or Al-h, is a paramagnetic centre, is therefore detectable by EPR, and have been extensively used for dating sediments [7, 8, 19, 20, 10, 12–18]. Ti centres have also been widely used for dating [7, 12, 19–21]. Upon room temperature irradiation, Ti^{4+} may trap an electron together with an alkali ion M^+ for charge compensation, forming $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$, where M^+ can be either Li^+ , H^+ or Na^+ [5]. Trapped-charge dating methods are based on the assumption that the natural growth of the signal of interest can be reproduced by laboratory irradiation, which leads to the construction of a dose response curve. The equivalent dose – a total dose of radiation absorbed by the crystal, is determined by extrapolation (in the case of additive dose protocols) or interpolation (in the case of regenerative protocols) of the dose response curve.

In many luminescence and EPR dating studies the choice of grain size fraction used for analysis has been most often dictated predominantly by the nature and availability of the material. Based on a series of previous research, Timar-Gabor et al. [22] showed there is a discrepancy of ages obtained by single aliquot regeneration protocol (SAR) OSL between different grain sizes and an age underestimation for finer grains and suggested a potentially worldwide phenomenon. However, defects giving rise to luminescence in quartz have not yet been unambiguously identified and their correlation with the defects detected by EPR remains unestablished. Consequently, the observations concerning grain size effects based on luminescence results are not directly transferable to EPR defects, which leaves this topic largely unexplored.

To fill this gap a systematic approach needs to be employed, starting with a thorough investigation of the dependence of EPR intensity of defects on the grain size, and followed by the experiments showing their behaviour when subjected to laboratory irradiation, which would expose any possible differences between fine- and coarse-grained quartz. It goes without saying, that such experimental studies should also be complemented by a development of appropriate models. The first objective was addressed by Timar-Gabor [23], by showing the dependence of EPR intensity of the main paramagnetic defects in quartz with grain size, for fraction 4–11, 63–90, 90–125, 125–180, and 180–250 μm . The intensity of the E_1' and Al-h signal in natural samples was found to decrease with increasing grain size, while $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0$ signals, detected only in coarse fractions, increased with increasing grain size. The second objective, involving the use of laboratory irradiation, is the subject of this work. To achieve any of these goals, or in fact to obtain any reliable dating, an accurate measurement of EPR signal intensity is crucial.

In this study we focus on the Al-h signal in fine (4–11 μm) and coarse (>60 μm) grains. The Al-h signal can only be measured by EPR at cryogenic temperatures, due to the very short spin-lattice relaxation time of the defect. It produces a complex EPR spectrum arising from the interaction of the unpaired electron with nearby magnetic nuclei. The Al-h signal consists of a central set of peaks around $g \approx 2.008$ displaying a distinct hyperfine structure, and much less intense set of peaks at about $g \approx 2.06$. In the early attempts of dating using the Al-h signal [24–26] different peaks from the central set were considered for evaluating its intensity. Their reliability was compared in a study by Lin et al. [27]. Eventually, a common approach proposed by Toyoda and Falguères [1] was adopted, and have been widely used ever since by the EPR dating community (e.g. [7, 10, 16–18]). It is based on the measurement of a peak-to-peak amplitude between the top of the first peak ($g = 2.018$) to the bottom of the last peak ($g = 1.993$) of the central part of ^{27}Al hyperfine structure. This method has been extremely useful, due to its simplicity, and the fact that it focuses on the most distinct peaks, which are clearly distinguishable even for very weak

signals. However, its applicability is sometimes limited by the presence of additional signals superimposed on the central part of the Al-h signal.

These additional signals are referred to as “peroxy” species, or sometimes for simplicity also as a peroxy centre (singular), although their spectrum is clearly composed of many overlapping signals. They are visible most clearly at room temperature, when the Al-h is not detectable. Friebele et al. [28] first established a peroxy radical in neutron or gamma-ray irradiated ^{17}O -enriched fused silica and suggested it to derive from pre-existing bridging peroxy linkages ($\equiv\text{Si}-\text{O}-\text{O}-\text{Si}\equiv$, where \equiv represents three Si-O bonds), which shed an electron to form peroxy radicals by irradiation and/or thermal treatment. Peroxy radicals in crystalline SiO_2 (α -quartz) have been suggested by several EPR studies and established by Botis et al. [29, 30], Nilges et al. [31, 32], and Pan et al. [33, 34] in their very detailed studies. Based on their research it was concluded that most of the discrepancies in the literature concerning the g-factor values, linewidths and hyperfine structure reported for the peroxy centres, can be attributed to incompletely resolved site splittings in previous X- and Q-band studies. For an in-depth investigation of these species higher microwave frequencies should be applied, and the accessibility of such equipment is very limited. Despite the wealth of information provided by these studies, there are still many unanswered questions regarding the nature of these signals, answers to which are essential considering their relevance in EPR dating and provenance investigations. It should be noted, that apart of the peroxy centres, another type of oxygen excess centres has been identified, namely non-bridging oxygen hole centre (NBOHC), described as oxygen dangling bonds $\equiv\text{Si}-\text{O}\cdot$ (where \cdot represents an unpaired electron) [35]. For simplicity however, in this study we use the term “peroxy” to describe all the signals observed between $g \approx 2.01$ and $g \approx 1.99$ at room temperature, with the exception of E' and Ge centres.

The complexity of the peroxy spectrum, combined with the limitations of the X-band spectroscopy routinely used for dating, makes the attempts of isolating these signals to obtain an undisturbed signal of the Al-h centre extremely challenging. Perhaps for this reason, the issue of the peroxy signals interfering with the Al-h measurements has been largely ignored in the literature. However, some amendments have been occasionally employed to circumvent the problem, such as subtracting the overlapping peroxy signal intensity using its EPR signal intensity after annealing [36]. The assumption here is that the peroxy signal does not change neither with heating nor with the dose of irradiation, and the same signal can be used for subtraction at low and high doses. While the latter assumption is generally accepted in the case of coarse grains, this has not been confirmed for fine grains. Indeed, Timar-Gabor [23] reported on a dose-dependent signal at $g \approx 2.011$ detected in fine-grained fraction of quartz, which suggests that this approach might not be applicable in every case. Moreover, it introduces additional uncertainty related to the determination of the peroxy signal intensity. Another approach, used by Tsukamoto et al. (2018) for the Al-h measurements conducted at 123 K, when the ^{27}Al hyperfine structures were not visible, was based on the measurement of the peak-to-peak intensity of the first central peak. It was reported to be consistent with the peak-to-peak intensity of the whole peak minus the intensity of the peroxy centre, which was measured at 183 K. No significant changes in the peroxy centre intensity were observed when raising the temperature from 123 to 183 K, and the Al-h signal at 183 K became almost undetectable. As in the previous example, this method bears some additional uncertainties. Additionally, the authors noted that their measurements might not be directly comparable with other studies, which use the traditional approach. It is clear, that developing an alternative approach to measuring the Al-h signal intensity, not affected by the presence of the peroxy signals, would improve the accuracy of age determination, and therefore greatly benefit the EPR dating community.

The aforementioned study by Timar-Gabor [23], conducted on several samples including two (ROX 1.14 and STY 1.10) studied in this work, shown that peroxy signals have significantly higher intensities in fine grains (4–11 μm) and decrease when grain size increases. Extended etching experiments resulted in obtaining partial evidence that these

defects are concentrated in damaged areas of the grains. The weaker signals of peroxy centres would suggest that coarser fractions should be preferred for conventional EPR dating using the approach of Toyoda and Falguères [1] to measuring the Al-h intensity. However, assuming that the issue of accurate determination of Al-h signal intensity could be solved, finer grains would not have to be automatically dismissed solely on that basis, especially as they are the main constituents of many sedimentary archives such as loess, lake or marine sediments. That would allow for a thorough comparison of the properties of the Al-h signal observed in fine and coarse grains and open a possibility of EPR dating based on fine grains, which has not been discussed before.

In this work we propose an alternative method of evaluating the Al-h signal intensity, which circumvents the issue of interfering peroxy signals. The results obtained for the new approach and the standard approach by Toyoda and Falguères [1] are compared using the measurements of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90, 125-180 μm) quartz separates from thoroughly investigated loess palaeosol sites in Eastern Europe (Roxolany, Stayky and Mircea Vodă), used in the previous investigations carried out by our group. By comparing the experimental spectra with a simulated signal of the Al-h centre, we evaluate the overestimation which results from using the standard approach, for different doses of radiation up to 40 000 Gy. We then use the dose response curves constructed from the intensities obtained with the new approach to compare, for the first time, the response of the Al-h signal to laboratory irradiation displayed by the fine- and coarse-grained fractions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Samples

Experiments presented in this study have been conducted on archived quartz separates of different grain sizes from the previous investigations carried out by our group.

Sample Rox 1.14 originates from Roxolany loess palaeosol section, Southern Ukraine and was collected below the Brunhes/Matuyama polarity transition. The results of EPR dating using a multi-centre approach, along with optically stimulated investigations using both the standard single aliquot regenerative (SAR) multi grain OSL procedure as well as single grain investigations are presented in detail in [37].

Quartz sample Sty 1.10 comes from Stayky loess palaeosol section, Northern Ukraine. The OSL chronology of this section as well as extended SAR-OSL dose response curves on the Styky samples are presented in detail in [38].

Sample 2MV 80 was collected near the village of Mircea Vodă, which is situated in the Dobrogea plateau, in SE Romania, about 15 km from the Danube River. Optical dating results for this site were published in [39] (including this sample) and in [9, 40] (previous sampling).

Preparation protocol, following the standard OSL preparation guidelines, has been described in detail in the aforementioned references, as well as in [23].

The selection of samples for the current study was based on the availability of sufficient material for EPR investigation and the high purity of the quartz extracts, as confirmed by routine tests in OSL dating as well as by scanning electron microscopy imaging coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) [23].

2.2 EPR measurements

EPR measurements were performed on an X band Bruker EMX Plus spectrometer at the Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. All samples were placed in quartz glass tubes filled with a mass of 200 mg \pm 10% for coarse grains ($>$ 63 μm) and 100 mg \pm 10% for fine grains, by maintaining the same volume, and the measurements later normalized to 100 mg for inter-comparison. Care was taken that all samples are centred inside the cavity. Samples were rotated in the cavity using a programmable goniometer and measured at 3 different angles (every 120°, 1 scan per angle). Measurements were usually

repeated 2–5 times at a few weeks interval. Details of reproducibility tests were described in [23]. A mean EPR intensity was used for constructing a dose response curve, and standard error was indicated in all the plots. Exposure of samples to sunlight during measurements was restricted to a minimum. Measurements were carried out at 90 K for Al-h centres and at room temperature (295 K) for peroxy centres, using a variable temperature unit. Spectra were acquired using the following settings: 3350 ± 150 G scanned magnetic field, modulation amplitude 1 G, modulation frequency 100 kHz, microwave power 2 mW, conversion time 40 ms, time constant 40 ms. Baseline correction was performed when necessary, using Bruker's Xenon software.

Samples were gamma irradiated with doses up to 10 000 Gy on top of the natural dose for sample ROX 1.14 and up to 40 000 Gy for samples STY 1.10 and 2MV 80. Due to the limited availability of the material less aliquots could be obtained for coarse than for fine fraction. Gamma irradiations were performed at room temperature at the Department of Health Technology at DTU (Dosimetry Research Unit) in Denmark using a calibrated ^{60}Co gamma cell with a dose rate of 2 Gy/s (dose rate to water) at the time of irradiation. Dose rate to quartz was estimated to be 96% of dose rate to water based on Monte Carlo simulation considering the irradiation geometry used.

2.3 Al-h signal simulations

Al-h signal was simulated with EasySpin [41], using parameters listed in **Table 1**. Initial parameters were based on [6, 42], and adjusted to fit the experimental spectra. The values of quadrupole splitting were used as in [42] with no adjustments. When comparing with an experimental spectrum, an average of baseline-corrected experimental spectra obtained for a given dose was used. A spectrum recorded at microwave frequency of 9.420796 GHz was chosen as a reference, and magnetic field values for all spectra were adjusted to match the position of the signal. A simulated spectrum was shown in **Fig. 1**, together with the main g-factor values mentioned in the text.

Table 1. Spin Hamiltonian parameters used for simulating $[\text{AlO}_4]^\ominus$ spectrum. A – hyperfine splitting, Q – quadrupole splitting, $S = 1/2$, ^{27}Al ($I = 5/2$), Lorentzian peak-to-peak linewidth 0.185 mT.

Parameter	x	y	z
g-factor	2.0603	2.0083	2.0021
A (MHz)	14	17	18.2
A (mT)	0.499	0.606	0.649
Q (MHz)	-0.62	-0.43	1.05
Q (mT)	-0.022	-0.015	0.037

234

235

Figure 1. A simulated EPR signal of the Al-h centre with the g-factor values mentioned in the text. The parameters used for simulation were listed in **Table 1**.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Contribution of peroxy signals to Al-h signal measurements

Spectra of the Al-h and peroxy signals obtained for coarse and fine grains of quartz irradiated with different doses were compared based on three examples: sample ROX 1.14, STY 1.10 and 2MV 80. Quartz from these three samples is supposed to have different sources, and as such one expects them to have different types and concentrations of defects, which makes them great subjects for studying the diversity of signals recorded by EPR.

3.1.1. Sample ROX 1.14

Fig. 2 shows a comparison of coarse (125–180 μm) and fine (4–11 μm) quartz EPR spectra of sample ROX 1.14 acquired at 90 K and at room temperature. Both fractions exhibit clear differences in the shape of the spectra. Experimental spectra of natural and additionally irradiated (with 1000 and 10 000 Gy) samples recorded at 90 K were overlaid with a simulated spectrum of Al-h (**Fig. 2a, b**). The shape of experimental spectra differs from the simulated one, which is caused by overlapping with signals assigned to the so-called peroxy species. The difference between Al-h simulation and experimental spectra recorded at 90 K is much more significant in case of fine grains, as the peroxy signals in 4–11 μm quartz are much stronger than in the bigger fractions, which was previously reported by Timar-Gabor [23]. In the case of coarse grains, this difference is visible only in the centre of the spectra and remains more pronounced for the smaller doses of irradiation.

The peroxy signals can be clearly registered at room temperature, when Al-h signal is not detectable (**Fig. 2c, d**). The structure of the spectra is complex and consists of several overlapping signals. Their detailed characterisation and interpretation have been a subject of several studies (e.g. [29–34]) and is beyond the scope of this work. What is relevant for this study is whether the intensity of some of these signals depends on the dose of irradiation, an issue which, to our knowledge, has not been addressed in the literature. The only exception is a mention of a dose-dependent signal at $g \approx 2.011$ detected by Timar-Gabor [23] in fine grains. The spectra of coarse-grained quartz shown in **Fig. 2c** indicates that only two signals, at $g \approx 2.000$ and $g \approx 1.996$, increase with the applied dose, while the rest does not show any changes. The signal at $g \approx 2.000$ can be ascribed to the E' centre and the peak at $g \approx 1.996$ to Ge centre, namely $[\text{GeO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0$ [6]. The peroxy signals detected in fine grains (**Fig. 2d**) are much stronger and the presence of some additional peaks is visible. In addition to the E' signal observed at $g \approx 1.999$ and the Ge signal at $g \approx 1.994$, at least two other signals, at $g \approx 2.009$ and $g \approx 2.001$, also show an increase with an increasing dose. The presence of these dose-dependent signals strongly influences the overall shape of the spectrum at high doses. The precise relationship between the intensity of these signals and the dose of laboratory irradiation cannot be determined at this point, as it requires separating them from the overlapping peaks, which is not possible without the aid of simulations, and/or measurements at higher microwave frequencies.

As the peroxy signals in 125–180 μm fraction of ROX 1.14, and most of them in case of fine grains, are not dose-dependent, their contribution to the overall intensity of the signals registered in the considered range at low temperature decreases with the dose of radiation, due to the increase of the Al-h signal. For coarse grains (**Fig. 2a**) the experimental spectrum at high doses is very close in shape to the simulated one, while for fine grains (**Fig. 2b**) the difference is still clearly visible.

When overlaying the experimental spectrum with a simulated one, we were faced with the issue of properly adjusting the amplitude of the latter. Since the central part of experimental spectra has proven to be distorted, to a varying degree, it should not be used as a reference point to adjust the simulated spectra. Therefore, a logical course of action

Figure 2. EPR spectra of coarse (125–180 μm) and fine (4–11 μm) fraction of sample ROX 1.14 natural and additionally irradiated with 1000 and 10 000 Gy, recorded at 90 K (**a**, **b**, respectively) and at room temperature (**c**, **d**, respectively), and simulated spectra of Al-h signal (in red). Amplitudes A_{exp} , A_{sim} , B_{exp} and B_{sim} were marked with arrows. Major dose-dependent signals observed at room temperature were marked with blue dashed lines. The 90 K spectra for coarse grains were multiplied by a factor of 2.6.

The interference of peroxy signals may naturally cause problems for accurate measurements of Al-h signal intensity. A well-established method of measuring the intensity of Al-h signal is based on measurement of peak-to-peak amplitude between the top of the first peak of the central signal ($g = 2.018$) to the bottom of the last peak ($g = 1.993$) (see **Fig. 1**) [1]. In **Fig. 2a** and **b** we marked the amplitudes measured using this approach (denoted further as “A”), obtained from experimental (A_{exp}) and simulated (A_{sim}) spectra of ROX 1.14 sample. As demonstrated for the additional dose of 10 000 Gy, both A_{exp} and A_{sim} give basically the same value (less than 2% difference) for coarse grains at high doses. However, due to the bigger contribution of peroxy signals A_{exp} amplitude at low doses is slightly overestimated compared to A_{sim} , for the natural sample giving about 13% and for 1000 Gy about 5% higher value compared to A_{sim} . For fine grains the overestimation of A_{exp} compared to A_{sim} is much more significant. For the natural sample of 4–11 μm ROX 1.14 it amounts to approximately 54%, for natural + 1000 Gy about 38%, and for natural + 10 000 Gy about 27%, as a result of increasing contribution of dose-dependent Al-h signals and decreasing contribution of mostly non-dose-dependent peroxy signals.

It is therefore clear, that although the approach based on measuring the amplitude A works very well for samples of coarse-grained quartz which accumulated a high dose of irradiation, i.e. very old samples and laboratory-irradiated samples, it can result in a significant overestimation in case of fine-grained and young coarse-grained quartz, which can affect the slope of the dose response curve. A more reliable method for quantitatively describing the changes of Al-h concentration with the dose would be using the simulated signals and calculating the area under the curve by double integration. This value is directly proportional to spin concentration and will not be affected by any contributions from other paramagnetic species. Despite those advantages, this method is very time consuming, demands more signal processing and is not always accessible. However, as mentioned previously, adjusting the simulated spectrum to the experimental one requires a reference point (or to be precise a second reference point, the first being the baseline), which in this case was chosen as the centre of the peak around $g \approx 2.0603$ (see **Fig. 1**). This provides the possibility of obtaining a reliable measurement of the amplitude simply by measuring the peak-to-baseline height of this peak of the experimental spectra, further referred to as “B”. The values of B_{exp} and B_{sim} (**Fig. 2**) will therefore be, by definition, always equal to each other, for every example of coarse and fine spectra. This approach allows for a much more accurate representation of Al-h signal intensity for fine grains, and may also improve the measurements of coarse grains, particularly for younger samples.

To investigate the effect of this overestimation on the shape and slope of the dose response curve (DRC), two sets of DRCs were constructed for sample ROX 1.14 (coarse and fine grains), using amplitudes A_{exp} (DRC A) and B_{exp} (DRC B) (**Fig. 3 a,b**). A sum of two exponential functions was used to fit the datapoints.

Figure 3. Dose response curves obtained for samples ROX 1.14 125-180 μm (a) and 4-11 μm (b) by measuring amplitudes A_{exp} and B_{exp} . Data normalised by the maximum value.

As expected from the comparison between simulated and experimental spectra, the lower dose part of DRC A for coarse grains (Fig. 3a) bends upwards compared to the DRC B, due to the contribution from peroxy signals, while at higher doses curves A and B overlap. As a result, the equivalent dose obtained from DRC A is overestimated. The divergence between DRC A and B is more pronounced in the case of quartz fraction 4-11 μm (Fig. 3b). Because of the peroxy contribution DRC A has a much smaller slope, which leads to a considerable overestimation of the equivalent dose obtained from this curve, compared to curve B. It should be borne in mind that, while both these curves seem to almost overlap at high doses, the values of amplitude A are still over 25% overestimated compared to amplitude B at 10 000 Gy. Since the exact nature of dose dependency of the signals observed in the case of fine grains is not known, the relationship between A and B values for doses above 10 000 Gy cannot be predicted at this point, and may further affect the shape and slope of the DRC A.

3.1.2. Sample STY 1.10

The second example of comparison between Al-h measurements for coarse and fine grain spectra is sample STY 1.10 (Fig. 4). The spectra of 125-180 μm fraction demonstrate a similar situation as for ROX 1.14 – the shape of experimental spectra differs slightly from simulation for smaller doses, and this difference becomes less significant as the radiation dose increases (Fig. 4a). The value of A_{exp} amplitude overestimates A_{sim} by about 13% for the natural signal, and about 5% for 1000 Gy and 10 000 Gy. For fine grains represented by a 4 – 11 μm fraction (Fig. 4b), the spectra for the natural sample, and the sample irradiated with 1000 Gy show differences between simulation and experiment analogous to the ones observed for sample ROX 1.14. Due to the contribution from peroxy signals A_{exp} overestimates A_{sim} by about 24% for the natural, and about 21% for 1000 Gy irradiated sample. For higher doses however, the situation becomes even more complex, as the overestimation of A_{exp} compared to A_{sim} increases again, to about 30% for 10 000 Gy. The explanation for this fact comes from analysing the peroxy signals observed at room temperature (Fig. 4c, d). While the spectra of coarse grains (Fig. 4c), as in the case of the sample ROX 1.14 (Fig. 2c), do not show significant changes as the dose increases, with only the Ge signal at $g \approx 1.996$ and E' signal at $g \approx 2.000$ being more prominent at high doses, the spectra of fine grains (Fig. 4d) exhibit some additional signals which increase their intensity with the laboratory dose. Most of them – the signal at $g \approx 2.002$, 2.010, the Ge signal ($g \approx 1.995$) and E' signal ($g \approx 2.000$), are also detected in the sample ROX 1.14 (Fig. 2d), but two other signals: at $g \approx 1.991$ and 2.016 are not. In particular, the signal at $g \approx 2.016$ exhibits a considerable growth, and due to its position, almost coinciding with the top of the first peak of the central Al-h signal ($g = 2.018$) used for A_{exp} estimation, it strongly affects the outcome of this measurement for higher doses. As a result, A_{exp} amplitude obtained for

337

338

339

340

341

342

343

344

345

346

347

348

349

350

351

352

353

354

355

356

357

358

359

360

361

362

363

364

365

366

367

368

369

370

371

372

373

374

375

376

377

fine grains gives unreliable measurements not only for lower, but also for higher doses, 378
making it unsuitable for the Al-h intensity determination. It is worth mentioning, that at 379
first glance, the low-temperature spectrum of STY 1.10 irradiated with 10 000 Gy does not 380
show clear signs of distortion around $g = 2.018$, as it still resembles the shape of Al-h signal 381
quite well, which can be very misleading, as it encourages the attempts of measuring A_{exp} . 382
It is only through analysing the room temperature measurements that the dose-dependent 383
nature of the signal at $g \approx 2.016$ can be revealed. In cases such as this, measuring A_{exp} , 384
although technically possible, results in unreliable data, leading to a distorted shape of 385
the dose-response curve. Amplitude B, however, remains unaffected by the contribution 386
of other signals, and therefore provides a reliable representation of the Al-h signal inten- 387
sity changes. 388

389

390

Figure 4. EPR spectra of coarse (125-180 μm) and fine (4-11 μm) fraction of sample STY 1.10 natural and additionally irradiated with 1000 and 10 000 Gy, recorded at 90 K (a, b, respectively) and at room temperature (c, d, respectively), and simulated spectra of Al-h signal (in red). Amplitudes A_{exp} , A_{sim} , B_{exp} and B_{sim} were marked with arrows. Major dose-dependent signals observed at room temperature were marked with blue dashed lines. The 90 K spectra for coarse grains were multiplied by a factor of 5.9.

391
392
393
394
395
396
397

3.1.3. Sample 2MV 80

The third example is based on the measurements of the sample 2MV 80 (Fig. 5). The spectra recorded at 90 K for coarse grains (Fig. 5a), in this case represented by a 63-90 μm fraction, show a more significant distortion than in the case of samples ROX 1.14 and STY 1.14. This is most likely due to the smaller size of the coarse grains – 63-90 μm instead of 125-180 μm as for the other two samples. As showed by Timar-Gabor [23] the intensity of the peroxy signals decreases with increasing grain size. For the natural sample A_{exp} overestimates A_{sim} value by as much as 82%, for 500 Gy by 62%, and for 5000 Gy by 44%. A small part of this overestimation might be attributed to performing a baseline correction, as the original baselines displayed a steeper slope and more complex shape, but even then, the differences between A_{exp} and A_{sim} are still very considerable. Due to a limited availability of coarse material less additional doses could be investigated, therefore the overestimation present at 10 000 Gy could not be determined. The spectra recorded at room temperature resemble those obtained for samples ROX 1.14 and STY 1.10, with the same dose-dependent signals at $g \approx 2.000$ and $g \approx 1.996$, ascribed to the E' and Ge centre, respectively, being visible.

For fine grains (Fig. 5b), the same as for sample ROX 1.14 and STY 1.10, a contribution of the peroxy signals in the central part of the spectrum is clearly visible, leading to an overestimation of A_{exp} by 50% compared to A_{sim} for the natural and 64% for 1000 Gy irradiated sample. At the higher doses, as shown for 10 000 Gy, the spectrum becomes very distorted, to the point that the measurement of A_{exp} is basically impossible, as it is clearly too affected by the overlapping signals. Measurements performed at room temperature (Fig. 5d) show the same dose-dependent signals as in the case of the samples ROX.1.14 and STY.1.10 – at $g \approx 2.010$, 2.002, and at $g \approx 1.999$ (E' centre) and 1.995 (Ge centre), as well as very strong dose-dependent signals at $g \approx 2.015$ and $g \approx 1.991$ observed also in sample STY 1.10, in addition the non-dose-dependent signals, visible also in coarse grains. In the case of samples like 2MV 80, with very strong dose-dependent signals overlapping with the Al-h signal, the measurement of the amplitude B is not only more reliable, but it appears to be the only viable option for obtaining the Al-h amplitude, without the use of simulations. It should be noted that the presence of dose-dependent signals will also cause problems when attempting to remove the peroxy signals by subtracting the spectra recorded after heating (as done by Richer & Tsukamoto [36]), since the peroxy spectrum will look differently for every dose, and the heating will likely affect the ratio of dose-dependent and non-dose-dependent peroxy signals. These arguments further advocate for using the amplitude B for Al-h intensity determination for both fine and coarse grains.

The comparison between the results obtained for the three presented examples by measuring the amplitude A and B shows the advantage of using the amplitude B for the Al-h intensity estimation. Contrary to the amplitude A, it is not affected by the peroxy signals present in the centre of the analysed range and therefore can provide more accurate results, or in fact any results in the cases where a spectrum is too distorted to allow for an estimation of the amplitude A. The measurements of the amplitude B were used in the second part of this study to compare the response of coarse and fine grains of quartz to laboratory irradiation.

3.2. Comparison of DRCs of coarse and fine grains

Dose response curves obtained using the amplitude B_{exp} were used for comparing the response of coarse and fine grains of quartz to laboratory irradiation (Fig. 6). Behaviour of the Al-h signal was investigated up to 10 000 Gy on top of the natural dose for sample ROX 1.14 and up to 40 000 Gy for samples STY 1.10 and 2MV 80. Due to the limited availability of the material less aliquots could be obtained for coarse than for fine fraction. No correction for the residual dose was applied.

Figure 5. EPR spectra of coarse (63-90 μm) and fine (4-11 μm) fraction of sample 2 MV 80 natural and additionally irradiated with 500 and 5000 Gy for coarse, and 1000 and 10 000 Gy for fine grains, recorded at 90 K (a, b, respectively) and at room temperature (c, d, respectively), and simulated spectra of Al-h signal (in red). Amplitudes A_{exp} , A_{sim} , B_{exp} and B_{sim} were marked with arrows. Major dose-dependent signals observed at room temperature were marked with blue dashed lines. The 90 K spectra for coarse grains were multiplied by a factor of 5.6.

Figure 6. Dose response curves for the amplitude B_{exp} obtained for fine (4–11 μm) and coarse (125–180 μm) grains of samples ROX 1.14 (a), STY 1.10 (b), and fine (4–11 μm) and coarse (63–90 μm) grains of sample 2MV 80 (c). Data were normalised to the maximum datapoint (a); maximum datapoint for fine grains and the respective fit point for coarse grains (b), maximum datapoint for fine grains and overlaid on the curve for coarse grains (c).

A note of caution regarding the fitting is necessary before proceeding to describe these results. A sum of two saturating exponential functions was used to fit the data. This choice was dictated by the results obtained in a recent study by Benzyd & Timar-Gabor [43], where a phenomenological model of Al-h formation upon room temperature irradiation was proposed. In this model the Al-h centre is considered to be formed upon laboratory irradiation by two processes: (i) directly by transforming $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ into Al-h, and (ii) indirectly by transforming $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ into $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{H}^+]^0$, and then $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{H}^+]^0$ into Al-h.

458

459

460

461

462

463

464

465

466

467

468

469

470

By assuming that the dissociation rates of these centres are proportional to their concentrations, the model shows that the increase of Al-h EPR signal with dose can be well described by a sum of two exponential functions. Benzid & Timar-Gabor, however, acknowledge the hazards of interpreting the parameters derived through fitting with multiple exponentials, stating that for quantitative assumptions using the derived parameters to be made, the DRC needs to be raised until full saturation. It was shown previously by Timar-Gabor et al. [22] for DRCs obtained for OSL signals fitted with a sum of two saturating exponentials that the obtained parameters depend on the maximum given dose, unless the DRC is constructed to high enough doses in order to reach full saturation. As clear from the Fig. 6, this is not the case for the DRCs constructed in the current study, therefore we refrain from deriving any conclusions based on parameters obtained from the fittings. As such, the fitted curves presented in Fig. 6 should be regarded primarily as a visual aid in comparing the response to laboratory irradiation. Additionally, due to a smaller number of datapoints for the coarse-grained samples STY 1.10 and 2MV 80 and their noticeable scatter, for STY 1.10 fitting had to be done by fixing some of the parameters to obtain visually best fit, and for 2MV 80 it was abandoned altogether.

Proceeding to the comparison of fine and coarse quartz DRCs, it is immediately apparent from Fig. 6a, that both 4-11 μm and 125-180 μm fractions of ROX 1.14 sample show almost identical shape of the DRC. While the number of datapoints is limited, it can be assumed that the effect of increasing laboratory dose on the Al-h signal, even if not identical, is remarkably similar in fine and coarse grains. Some differences between the shapes of both DRCs can be observed for the sample STY 1.10 (Fig. 6b), namely the DRC obtained by fitting for coarse (125-180 μm) grains seems to saturate faster. However, the shape of the fitted curves is likely affected by a noticeable scatter of the datapoints and the absence of data for coarse grains above 20 000 Gy, so the divergence observed in Fig. 6b may very well be exaggerated. As mentioned before, the data obtained for the coarse (63-90 μm) fraction of the sample 2MV 80 (Fig. 6c) did not allow for a satisfactory fitting, as the shape of the fitted curve would be largely affected by an arbitrary choice of parameters. Instead, the datapoints were overlaid on the DRC obtained for fine grains. As far as the doses up to 5000 Gy are concerned the data for coarse and fine grains is in very good agreement, suggesting that in this range there are no significant differences in the behaviour of Al-h signal in coarse and fine grains of this sample. Despite the aforementioned issues with the fitting, it can be observed simply by visually following the datapoints, that in all three cases the intercept of the DRCs with the x axis seem to be the same for both fractions.

It can therefore be stated that no significant divergence in the behaviour of the Al-h signal with the increasing radiation dose in the investigated range can be observed between the fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm and 125-180 μm) grains of quartz studied in this work. A logical conclusion is to assume that the Al-h centre formation in fine and coarse grains to artificial radiation is governed by the same processes. To our knowledge, the influence of grain size on the formation of the Al-h centre has not been discussed in the literature. The phenomenological model of Al-h formation upon laboratory irradiation at room temperature proposed by Benzid & Timar-Gabor [43] does not suggest that this process would be significantly different for coarse and fine grains. As Al-h centres are extrinsic impurity related defects it is to be expected that they have a relatively homogeneous distribution in the volume of a sedimentary quartz grain. Indeed, Timar-Gabor [23] reported that no significant effect could be observed when measuring Al-h signals as function of etching time. More experimental and theoretical studies are certainly needed to further examine the mechanism of the Al-h centre formation, however our results show that in the first approximation the response of both fine- and coarse-grained quartz to artificial irradiation is remarkably similar.

Should coarse and fine grains of quartz therefore give the same equivalent dose when dated using the Al-h centre? The answer to this question requires a separate consideration and cannot be answered at this point. It is generally accepted that sunlight exposure does not completely bleach the EPR intensity of Al-h, and the signal is reset only

to a non-bleachable residual level (e.g., [7, 8, 44–48]). Our study focuses on the unbleached samples, which have a residual signal composed of bleachable and unbleachable components. These components can be of different magnitudes for coarse and fine grains, and should be determined separately for every fraction, which is beyond the scope of this work. To our knowledge, the only study showing the effects of grain size on the results of EPR dating of quartz was done by Liu et al. [49] for Ti-Li centre in fluvial and lacustrine sediments. They assumed complete bleaching and reported that for the grain sizes above 100 μm the equivalent dose was decreasing with the increase of the grain size. However, for the smallest fraction (50–100 μm , which in our study would still be considered coarse), the equivalent dose was smaller than for the larger fraction. They also showed that the beta irradiation dose rate of the grains with different sizes accounts for only about 6% of the total deviation of the dating results, making it far less significant than the effect of grain size on EPR sensitivity. No similar studies have been conducted on the Al-h centre in sedimentary quartz. It should be mentioned that the effect the size of grains has on the obtained equivalent dose was investigated for E' and Al-h centre in quartz from fault gouge (e.g. [50, 51]), but due to the different mechanism involved in resetting the signal (mechanical deformation and high temperature) these results cannot be of use for other types of environments.

The behaviour of the Al-h signal in coarse and fine grains upon laboratory irradiation might differ from the behaviour observed in nature. Depending on the grain size the amount of alpha and beta radiation penetrating the grain will be different, influencing the formation of defects. Understanding the processes induced in fine and coarse grains by gamma radiation in a controlled laboratory environment is the first step towards a development of a comprehensive model. The grain size effect on the formation and bleachability of the Al-h centre under natural conditions needs to be thoroughly studied, before any conclusions are drawn regarding the overall result of EPR dating using different fractions. We hope that our work will stimulate such studies.

5. Conclusions

We examined the Al-h and peroxy EPR spectra of fine (4–11 μm) and coarse (63–90, 125–180 μm) sedimentary quartz separates extracted from three well-characterised samples collected from thoroughly investigated sites (Roxolany, Stayky and Mircea Vodă). Based on the data presented in this work, as well as in the study conducted by Timar-Gabor [23], it is clear that Al-h measurements of fine grains are affected by the presence of peroxy signals to a much bigger extent than coarse grains. However, the degree to which it affects the standard amplitude measurement following the approach of Toyoda and Falguères [1] seems to be sample-dependent. It ranges from causing an overestimation, which is much stronger for smaller doses (sample ROX 1.14), to a complete distortion of the spectra at high doses (sample 2MV 80), due to the presence of dose-dependent peroxy signals in fine grains. For a proper understanding of the observed differences a much bigger set of samples would certainly have to be analysed, which is not an easy task, since it requires a large amount of material from different sites divided into fractions.

The new approach to measuring the Al-h signal amplitude proposed in this study, focusing on the peak-to-baseline amplitude of the part of the signal at $g \approx 2.0603$ has the potential of providing more accurate results. This region of the spectrum is not affected by the strong peroxy signals overlapping the central part of the Al-h signal and causing the overestimation. It should be mentioned that while very useful for samples with strong Al-h signals, as the ones investigated here, it might not be applicable to very weak signals. This part of the Al-h spectrum is considerably less intense than the central signal typically used for measuring the amplitude, and in case of some samples it may simply be undetectable. Additionally, more studies are needed on the individual signals composing the peroxy spectra, in order to rule out the possibility of some weaker lower-field peaks being present around $g \approx 2.0603$, which could affect the amplitude measurement following this new approach.

We compared the response of the Al-h signal to laboratory irradiation displayed by the fine- and coarse-grained fractions, which has not been previously shown in the literature. The shapes of dose response curves constructed for coarse and fine grains using the new approach show a considerable similarity, which suggests that the Al-h centre formation in fine and coarse grains upon artificial radiation follows the same pattern. These observations have significant implications for the dating community and will hopefully inspire more research, experimental and theoretical, allowing for a thorough comparison of dating results obtained for different fractions of sedimentary quartz, which in turn will deepen our understanding of the underlying processes and increase the accuracy of EPR dating.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Z.K. and A.T.-G.; investigation, Z.K. and A.T.-G.; writing – original draft preparation, Z.K.; writing – review & editing, A.T.-G.; visualization, Z.K.; supervision, A.T.-G.; project administration, A.T.-G.; funding acquisition, A.T.-G. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This study has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme ERC-2015-STG (grant agreement No [678106]).

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data analysed in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Toyoda, S.; Falguères, C. The Method to Represent the ESR Signal Intensity of the Aluminum Hole Center in Quartz for the Purpose of Dating. *Adv. ESR Appl.*, **2003**, *20*, 7–10.
2. Preusser, F.; Chithambo, M. L.; Götze, T.; Martini, M.; Ramseyer, K.; Sendezera, E. J.; Susino, G. J.; Wintle, A. G. Quartz as a Natural Luminescence Dosimeter. *Earth-Science Rev.*, **2009**, *97* (1–4), 184–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.09.006>.
3. Götze, J. Chemistry, Textures and Physical Properties of Quartz – Geological Interpretation and Technical Application. *Mineral. Mag.*, **2009**, *73* (4), 645–671. <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.2009.073.4.645>.
4. Malik, D. M.; Kohnke, E. E.; Sibley, W. A. Low-temperature Thermally Stimulated Luminescence of High Quality Quartz. *J. Appl. Phys.*, **1981**, *52* (5), 3600–3605. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.329092>.
5. Toyoda, S. Paramagnetic Lattice Defects in Quartz for Applications to ESR Dating. *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2015**, *30*, 498–505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2015.05.010>.
6. Ikeya, M. *New Applications of Electron Spin Resonance: Dating, Dosimetry and Microscopy*; World Scientific: Singapore, New Jersey, London, Hong Kong, 1993.
7. Duval, M.; Arnold, L. J.; Guilarte, V.; Demuro, M.; Santonja, M.; Pérez-González, A. Electron Spin Resonance Dating of Optically Bleached Quartz Grains from the Middle Palaeolithic Site of Cuesta de La Bajada (Spain) Using the Multiple Centres Approach. *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2017**, *37*, 82–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2016.09.006>.
8. Tsukamoto, S.; Long, H.; Richter, M.; Li, Y.; King, G. E.; He, Z.; Yang, L.; Zhang, J.; Lambert, R. Quartz Natural and Laboratory ESR Dose Response Curves: A First Attempt from Chinese Loess. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2018**, *120* (August), 137–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.09.008>.
9. Timar-Gabor, A.; Vandenberghe, D. A. G.; Vasiliu, S.; Panaoitu, C. E.; Panaiotu, C. G.; Dimofte, D.; Cosma, C. Optical Dating of Romanian Loess: A Comparison between Silt-Sized and Sand-Sized Quartz. *Quat. Int.*, **2011**, *240* (1–2), 62–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2010.10.007>.
10. Tissoux, H.; Toyoda, S.; Falguères, C.; Voinchet, P.; Takada, M.; Bahain, J.-J.; Despriée, J. ESR Dating of Sedimentary Quartz

- from Two Pleistocene Deposits Using Al and Ti-Centers. *GEOCHR*, **2008**, *30* (1), 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10003-008-0004-y>. 624
625
11. Weil, J. A. A Review of Electron Spin Spectroscopy and Its Application to the Study of Paramagnetic Defects in Crystalline Quartz. *Phys. Chem. Miner.*, **1984**, *10* (4), 149–165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00311472>. 626
627
12. Duval, M.; Guilarte, V. ESR Dosimetry of Optically Bleached Quartz Grains Extracted from Plio-Quaternary Sediment: Evaluating Some Key Aspects of the ESR Signals Associated to the Ti-Centers. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2015**, *78*, 28–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2014.10.002>. 628
629
630
13. Laurent, M.; Falguères, C.; Bahain, J. .; Rousseau, L.; Van Vliet Lanoé, B. ESR Dating of Quartz Extracted from Quaternary and Neogene Sediments method, Potential and Actual Limits. *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **1998**, *17* (11), 1057–1062. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(97\)00101-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(97)00101-7). 631
632
633
14. Parés, J. M.; Álvarez, C.; Sier, M.; Moreno, D.; Duval, M.; Woodhead, J. D.; Ortega, A. I.; Campaña, I.; Rosell, J.; Bermúdez de Castro, J. M.; et al. Chronology of the Cave Interior Sediments at Gran Dolina Archaeological Site, Atapuerca (Spain). *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **2018**, *186*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2018.02.004>. 634
635
636
15. Rink, W. J.; Bartoll, J.; Schwarcz, H. P.; Shane, P.; Bar-Yosef, O. Testing the Reliability of ESR Dating of Optically Exposed Buried Quartz Sediments. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2007**, *42* (10), 1618–1626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2007.09.005>. 637
638
16. Tissoux, H.; Voinchet, P.; Lacquement, F.; Prognon, F.; Moreno, D.; Falguères, C.; Bahain, J.-J.; Toyoda, S. Investigation on Non-Optically Bleachable Components of ESR Aluminium Signal in Quartz. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2012**, *47* (9), 894–899. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2012.03.012>. 639
640
641
17. Voinchet, P.; Bahain, J. J.; Falguères, C.; Laurent, M.; Dolo, J. M.; Despriée, J.; Gageonnet, R.; Chaussé, C. ESR Dating of Quartz Extracted from Quaternary Sediments Application to Fluvial Terraces System of Northern France [Datation Par Résonance Paramagnétique Électronique (RPE) de Quartz Fluviaux Quaternaires: Application Aux Systèmes de Terrasses Du Nord. *Quaternaire*, **2004**, *15* (1), 135–141. <https://doi.org/10.3406/quate.2004.1761>. 642
643
644
645
18. Voinchet, P.; Yin, G.; Falguères, C.; Liu, C.; Han, F.; Sun, X.; Bahain, J. J. Dating of the Stepped Quaternary Fluvial Terrace System of the Yellow River by Electron Spin Resonance (ESR). *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2019**, *49* (November 2017), 278–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2018.08.001>. 646
647
648
19. Moreno, D.; Duval, M.; Rubio-Jara, S.; Panera, J.; Bahain, J. J.; Shao, Q.; Pérez-González, A.; Falguères, C. ESR Dating of Middle Pleistocene Archaeo-Paleontological Sites from the Manzanares and Jarama River Valleys (Madrid Basin, Spain). *Quat. Int.*, **2019**, *520*, 23–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2017.09.003>. 649
650
651
20. Moreno, D.; Gutiérrez, F.; Val, M. del; Carbonel, D.; Jiménez, F.; Jesús Alonso, M.; Martínez-Pillado, V.; Guzmán, O.; López, G. I.; Martínez, D. A Multi-Method Dating Approach to Reassess the Geochronology of Faulted Quaternary Deposits in the Central Sector of the Iberian Chain (NE Spain). *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2021**, *65* (April), 101185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2021.101185>. 652
653
654
21. Beerten, K.; Lomax, J.; Clémer, K.; Stesmans, A.; Radtke, U. On the Use of Ti Centres for Estimating Burial Ages of Pleistocene Sedimentary Quartz: Multiple-Grain Data from Australia. *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2006**, *1* (2), 151–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2006.05.037>. 655
656
657
22. Timar-Gabor, A.; Buylaert, J.-P.; Guralnik, B.; Trandafir-Antohei, O.; Constantin, D.; Anechitei-Deacu, V.; Jain, M.; Murray, A. S.; Porat, N.; Hao, Q.; et al. On the Importance of Grain Size in Luminescence Dating Using Quartz. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2017**, *106*, 464–471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2017.01.009>. 658
659
660
23. Timar-Gabor, A. Electron Spin Resonance Characterisation of Sedimentary Quartz of Different Grain Sizes. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2018**, *120* (May), 59–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.06.023>. 661
662
24. Yokoyama, Y.; Falgueres, C.; Quaegebeur, J. P. ESR Dating of Quartz from Quaternary Sediments: First Attempt. *Nucl. Tracks Radiat. Meas.*, **1985**, *10* (4–6), 921–928. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0735-245X\(85\)90109-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0735-245X(85)90109-7). 663
664
25. Toyoda, S.; Ikeya, M. ESR Dating of Quartz and Plagioclase from Volcanic Ashes Using E'1, A1 and Ti Centers. *Int. J. Radiat.* 665

- Appl. Instrumentation. Part D. Nucl. Tracks Radiat. Meas.*, **1991**, *18* (1–2), 179–184. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1359-0189\(91\)90110-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/1359-0189(91)90110-4). 666
26. Imai, N.; Shimokawa, K. ESR Dating of Quaternary Tephra from Mt. Osore-Zan Using Al and Ti Centres in Quartz. *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **1988**, *7* (3–4), 523–527. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791\(88\)90056-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791(88)90056-X). 667
668
27. Lin, M.; Yin, G.; Ding, Y.; Cui, Y.; Chen, K.; Wu, C.; Xu, L. Reliability Study on ESR Dating of the Aluminum Center in Quartz. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2006**, *41* (7–8), 1045–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2006.05.019>. 669
670
28. Friebele, E. J.; Griscom, D. L.; Stapelbroek, M.; Weeks, R. A. Fundamental Defect Centers in Glass: The Peroxy Radical in Irradiated, High-Purity, Fused Silica. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, **1979**, *42* (20), 1346–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.42.1346>. 671
672
29. Botis, S.; Nokhrin, S. M.; Pan, Y.; Xu, Y.; Bonli, T.; Sopuck, V. Natural Radiation-Induced Damage in Quartz. I. Correlations between Cathodoluminescence Colors and Paramagnetic Defects. *Can. Mineral.*, **2005**, *43* (5), 1565–1580. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gscanmin.43.5.1565>. 673
674
675
30. Botis, S. M.; Pan, Y.; Nokhrin, S.; Nilges, M. J. Natural Radiation-Induced Damage in Quartz. III. A New Ozonide Radical in Drusy Quartz from the Athabasca Basin, Saskatchewan. *Can. Mineral.*, **2008**, *46* (1), 125–138. <https://doi.org/10.3749/canmin.46.1.125>. 676
677
678
31. Nilges, M. J.; Pan, Y.; Mashkovtsev, R. I. Radiation-Damage-Induced Defects in Quartz. I. Single-Crystal W-Band EPR Study of Hole Centers in an Electron-Irradiated Quartz. *Phys. Chem. Miner.*, **2008**, *35* (2), 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-007-0203-5>. 679
680
681
32. Nilges, M. J.; Pan, Y.; Mashkovtsev, R. I. Radiation-Induced Defects in Quartz. III. Single-Crystal EPR, ENDOR and ESEEM Study of a Peroxy Radical. *Phys. Chem. Miner.*, **2009**, *36* (2), 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-008-0258-y>. 682
683
33. Pan, Y.; Nilges, M. J.; Mashkovtsev, R. I. Radiation-Induced Defects in Quartz. II. Single-Crystal W-Band EPR Study of a Natural Citrine Quartz. *Phys. Chem. Miner.*, **2008**, *35* (7), 387–397. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-008-0233-7>. 684
685
34. Pan, Y.; Nilges, M. J.; Mashkovtsev, R. I. Radiation-Induced Defects in Quartz: A Multifrequency EPR Study and DFT Modelling of New Peroxy Radicals. *Mineral. Mag.*, **2009**, *73* (4), 519–535. <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.2009.073.4.519>. 686
687
35. Skuja, L.; Ollier, N.; Kajihara, K. Luminescence of Non-Bridging Oxygen Hole Centers as a Marker of Particle Irradiation of α -Quartz. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2020**, *135* (April), 106373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2020.106373>. 688
689
36. Richter, M.; Tsukamoto, S. Investigation of Quartz Electron Spin Resonance Residual Signals in the Last Glacial and Early Holocene Fluvial Deposits from the Lower Rhine. *Geochronology*, **2022**, *4* (1), 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gchron-4-55-2022>. 690
691
37. Anechitei-Deacu, V.; Timar-Gabor, A.; Thomsen, K. J.; Buylaert, J.-P.; Jain, M.; Bailey, M.; Murray, A. S. Single and Multi-Grain OSL Investigations in the High Dose Range Using Coarse Quartz. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2018**, *120* (March), 124–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.06.008>. 692
693
694
38. Veres, D.; Tecsa, V.; Gerasimenko, N.; Zeeden, C.; Hambach, U.; Timar-Gabor, A. Short-Term Soil Formation Events in Last Glacial East European Loess, Evidence from Multi-Method Luminescence Dating. *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **2018**, *200*, 34–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2018.09.037>. 695
696
697
39. Groza-Săcaci, Ștefana-M.; Panaiotu, C.; Timar-Gabor, A. Single Aliquot Regeneration (SAR) Optically Stimulated Luminescence Dating Protocols Using Different Grain-Sizes of Quartz: Revisiting the Chronology of Mircea Vodă Loess-Paleosol Master Section (Romania). *Methods Protoc.*, **2020**, *3* (1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mps3010019>. 698
699
700
40. Timar, A.; Vandenberghe, D.; Panaiotu, E. C.; Panaiotu, C. G.; Necula, C.; Cosma, C.; van den haute, P. Optical Dating of Romanian Loess Using Fine-Grained Quartz. *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2010**, *5* (2–3), 143–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2009.03.003>. 701
702
703
41. Stoll, S.; Schweiger, A. EasySpin, a Comprehensive Software Package for Spectral Simulation and Analysis in EPR. *J. Magn. Reson.*, **2006**, *178* (1), 42–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmr.2005.08.013>. 704
705
42. Nuttall, R. H. D.; Weil, J. A. The Magnetic Properties of the Oxygen-Hole Aluminum Centers in Crystalline SiO₂. I. [AlO₄]⁰. *Can. J. Phys.*, **1981**, *59* (11), 1696–1708. <https://doi.org/10.1139/p81-227>. 706
707

-
43. Benzid, K.; Timar-Gabor, A. Phenomenological Model of Aluminium-Hole ([AlO₄/H⁺]₀) Defect Formation in Sedimentary Quartz upon Room Temperature Irradiation: Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) Study. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2020**, *130* (April 2019), 106187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2019.106187>. 708
709
710
44. Timar-Gabor, A.; Chruścińska, A.; Benzid, K.; Fitzsimmons, K. E.; Begy, R.; Bailey, M. Bleaching Studies on Al-Hole ([AlO₄/h]₀) Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) Signal in Sedimentary Quartz. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2020**, *130*, 106221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2019.106221>. 711
712
713
45. Tissoux, H.; Falguères, C.; Voinchet, P.; Toyoda, S.; Bahain, J. J.; Despriée, J. Potential Use of Ti-Center in ESR Dating of Fluvial Sediment. *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2007**, *2* (1–4), 367–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2006.04.006>. 714
715
46. Toyoda, S.; Voinchet, P.; Falguères, C.; Dolo, J. M.; Laurent, M. Bleaching of ESR Signals by the Sunlight: A Laboratory Experiment for Establishing the ESR Dating of Sediments. *Appl. Radiat. Isot.*, **2000**, *52* (5), 1357–1362. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-8043\(00\)00095-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-8043(00)00095-6). 716
717
718
47. Tsukamoto, S.; Porat, N.; Ankjærgaard, C. Dose Recovery and Residual Dose of Quartz ESR Signals Using Modern Sediments: Implications for Single Aliquot ESR Dating. *Radiat. Meas.*, **2017**, *106*, 472–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2017.02.010>. 719
720
48. Voinchet, P.; Falguères, C.; Laurent, M.; Toyoda, S.; Bahain, J. J.; Dolo, J. M. Artificial Optical Bleaching of the Aluminium Center in Quartz Implications to ESR Dating of Sediments. *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **2003**, *22* (10–13), 1335–1338. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(03\)00062-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(03)00062-3). 721
722
723
49. Liu, C.-R.; Yin, G.-M.; Han, F. Effects of Grain Size on Quartz ESR Dating of Ti–Li Center in Fluvial and Lacustrine Sediments. *Quat. Geochronol.*, **2015**, *30*, 513–518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2015.02.007>. 724
725
50. Buhay, W. M.; Schwarcz, H. P.; Grün, R. ESR Dating of Fault Gouge: The Effect of Grain Size. *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **1988**, *7* (3–4), 515–522. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791\(88\)90055-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791(88)90055-8). 726
727
51. Lee, H.-K.; Yang, J.-S. ESR Dating of the Wangsan Fault, South Korea. *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, **2003**, *22* (10–13), 1339–1343. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(03\)00018-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(03)00018-0). 728
729
730